

Influence of Leader Orientation, Working Spirit and Working Environment against Employee Performance in Hospital Pertamina Pangkalan Brandan

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to test and know more clearly how the influence of orientation leaders, morale, and the environment on the performance employee. The problem is that the author adopted, namely: whether orientation leaders, morale and working environment have a significant effect simultaneously and partially on the performance of employees Hospital Pertamina Pangkalan Brandan. This study uses a quantitative method involving 70 respondents. Collecting data is done using questionnaires division. The acquired data was analyzed using statistical formulas, using multiple linear regression analysis performed with SPSS version 23 program.

Results of regression analysis as follows:

$$Y = 2.861 + 0.308 X_1 + 0.120 X_2 + 0.446 + \varepsilon$$

Variable orientation of leaders has the greatest influence on the performance of employees 0.342. The results of the analysis using the coefficient of determination is known that 76.2% of the employee's performance variation can be explained by the orientation leaders, morale and working environment at the 0.05% level of confidence. While the remaining 23.8% is explained by other variables not included in this study. The results of multiple regression analysis showed that partial orientation leaders have significant influence on employee performance. The test results simultaneously show the orientation leaders, morale and working environment has a significant influence on employee performance.

Keywords: Orientation Leader, Morale, Work Environment, Performance Employee

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalization era, every company is required to have good management. A good company management is sure to improve the effectiveness of the company. The effectiveness of the company can be achieved well when its human resources are able to compete. Human resources are the most important asset to the organization, and must be developed where the essence serves as a driving factor for every activity within the company.

In order for the human resources in the organization or the company to work well, the leader plays an important role to influence and move the subordinates, focusing attention on the objectives, coordinating the changes, establishing personal contact with their followers, to achieve organizational objectives.

The spirit of work is also not detached from the good and comfortable working environment, as the perception of some employees provides different assessments of all aspects of the work environment. Environmental conditions are said to be good when human beings can carry out activities optimally, healthy, and comfortable and creates a harmonious relationship between employers and employees and between colleagues in the working environment. Here what is meant by the work environment is everything that exists around the workers that can affect itself in carrying out the tasks charged.

In the case of Hospital Pertamina Pangkalan Brandan based on initial observation, physical condition that looks narrow workspace, many files that overlap, partly under the table so it looks messy, work equipment is not neatly arranged, lighting in the waiting room is still lacking, but on the other side the patient waiting room has been look clean and comfortable. In this case the working spirit if not balanced with a supportive working environment will be difficult for employees to improve their performance.

In each company employees work in an organization is also influenced by many factors, but the progress or deterioration of a company is determined by the components in it. The increasing performance will be able to help the company to succeed in achieving its vision and mission, but conversely when the performance drops it will negatively affect the company.

The decrease in performance from some employees of Hospital Pertamina Pangkalan Brandan is caused by several factors, namely frustration, dissatisfaction in working, got pressure, saturated in an unsupportive atmosphere. Therefore, the performance of employees need to be repaired with alternative roads, among others, creating a supportive working environment, both physical and non-physical work environment, creating a relaxed atmosphere, providing opportunities for employees who excel to get promotions, etc.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Leader Orientation

Miftha Thoha (2006:255) a leader is a person who has the ability to lead, meaning it has the ability to influence another person or group without heeding the form of reason. The other opinion of Kartini Kartono (2008:33) The leader is a person who has the prowess and advantages of particularly prowess and excess in one field, so that he is able to influence others to jointly perform certain activities, for the achievement of one or several purposes.

Leader Orientation Indicator

The dimensions to be measured in this study refer to the concept developed by Bass & Avolio (1995). Task-oriented leadership variables are measured through three indicators:

- a. A conditional reward is a behaviour that always recognizes employee achievement and explains expectations.
- b. Active management with an exception is the behavior of the leader who will take action immediately to correct the problem and show the errors that occur.
- c. Passive management with exceptions is the behavior of the leader who will wait until the problem becomes chronic or seriously new to make corrections.

While the relationship-oriented leadership variables measured through five dimensions include:

- a. The ideal attribution is a leader who instills pride and builds subordinate confidence.
- b. The ideal behaviour is the leader who emphasizes the collective meaning of the mission and talks about its values and beliefs.
- c. Inspirational motivation is a leader capable of express a sense of enthusiasm, optimism, and self-confidence.
- d. Intlektual Stimulation is a leader who wants to develop, train and teach subordinates.
- e. The care of the individual is a leader who will acknowledge the subordinate's achievements and explain their expectations.

Spirit Of Work

According to Nitiesmito (2012:108) The spirit of work is to do the work more actively with the way to minimize confusion in the work, to strengthen the sense of responsibility and to accomplish the task but the time according to the set plan.

According to Hasibuan (2009:94) with the high spirit of work is a positive reaction in other words can finish the job with better results, the spirit of work has a concern about the activities of the company, so that the company or organization wants employees who have a high spirit of work. From some of the above opinion can be concluded that the spirit of work is the ability or willingness of each individual to know a group of people to cooperate with the active and disciplined and full of responsibilities accompanied his volunteering and willingness to achieve the objectives of the Organization.

Indicators Of Working Spirit

According to Nitisemito (2012; 45), indications showing the general tendency of low working spirit are low productivity, high attendance rate, high labour turnover, high level of damage, ubiquitous anxiety, frequent demands, and strikes. Based on indications that show the tendency of low working spirit, the characteristics of employee morale can be known from three indicators, namely:

- a. Organizational culture.
- b. Compensation.
- c. Motivation.

Understanding of The Work Environment

According to Nitisemito (Sedarmayanti, 2009:31) "work environment as everything around the workers that can affect himself in carrying out the duties charged". Another understanding of Sedarmayanti (2009:31) "The work environment is the whole tools and materials faced, the surrounding environment where a person works, the method of work, and the arrangement of his work both as an individual or as a group.

Indicators of Physical Work Environment

(Sedarmayanti, 2009:31) Indicators of physical work environment are:

- a. The Workplace Cleanliness, The Workplace Is Not Dirty And Neatly Arranged.
- b. Adequate Lighting And Lighting, Light Insufficient And Good Lighting System.
- c. Air Exchange, Air Circulation In The Workspace.
- d. Color, Coloring The Workspace Is Comfortable.
- e. Noise, Place and work space away from the noise.

Indicators of Non-Physical Work Environment

Wurasanto (2009) argues that there are several important elements in the formation of attitudes and behaviors of employees in a non-physical work environment, namely as follows:

- a. Supervision, which is done continuously by using a strict surveillance system
- b. Working atmosphere, which can provide encouragement and a high working spirit.
- c. The reward system (whether salary or other stimulant) is interesting.
- d. Treatment is good, humane, not likened to a robot or machine, the opportunity to develop a career as closely as possible according to each member's ability limit.
- e. There is a sense of security from the members, both in the office and outside the service.
- f. The relationship progresses in a harmonious, more informal, full of family.
- g. Members get fair and objective treatment.

Performance Sense

According to Hasibuan (2009:94) The performance of work achieved by a person in which the tugs will be charged is based on proficiency, experience, seriousness, and time. According to Rivai and Sagala (2009:269) stated that performance is a real behavior that is displayed every person as achievement of work produced by the employee in accordance with his role in the Organiorang.

Performance Indicators

According to (Hasibuan 2006:94) The performance indicators are:

- a. productivity is a concrete result (product) produced by an individual or group, during a certain time unit in a working process.
- b. Service quality, dynamic conditions that are influential with products, services, people, processes and environments that meet or exceed expectations.
- c. The responsiveness, the ability of the organization to recognize the needs of the community, to develop the agenda and priorities of services and develop public services programs according to the needs and aspirations of society

- d. The responsibility, which explains whether the implementation of public organization activities is conducted in accordance with the correct administrative principles or in accordance with the Organization's policies.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework According to Rusiadi (2013) states that the concept framework will link theoretically between research variables i.e. independent variables with dependent variables. In this case, to get a clearer understanding and sense of the influence of leader orientation, work spirit, and working environment towards employee performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This research draft is quantitative research, while the level of Explanative is an associative/correlational study which is a study aimed at knowing the relationship between two or more variables.

The population is a generalization area consisting of objects that have certain qualities and characteristics set by researchers to learn and then withdrawn (Sugiyono, 2009:72). The population in this study was 70 employees of Hospital Pertamina Pangkalan Brandan. Samples are partially or representatives of the population studied. When its subject is less than 100 it is better taken all, so the study is population research. If the number of subjects is greater than 100 can be taken 0% s. D 15% or 20%

or more (Sugiyono, 2009:135). Based on the above definition,

Data Analysis

1. Data Quality test
 - a. Validity test
 - b. Reliability test
2. Classic Assumption Test
 - a. Test Normality
 - b. Multicollinearity Test
 - c. Heteroskedasticity Test
3. Multiple linear regression analysis
$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_3X_3 + b_2X_2 + \epsilon$$
4. Conformity test (Test Goodness Of Fit)
 - a. Test F
 - b. Test T
 - c. Coefficient of determination (R^2)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Data Presenter

This research has 3 (three) free variables, namely the orientation of the leader, the working spirit and the working environment, as well as 1 (one) variable bonded that is the employee's performance. In the distribution of polls, each variable of 6 (six) items must be filled by respondents amounting to 70 people.

Poll answers are provided in 5 alternative answers:

- a. Very Sejutu (SS) with a score of 5
- b. Agree (S) with score 4
- c. Less concur (KS) with a score of 3
- d. Disagree (TS) with a score of 2
- e. Strongly disagree (STS) with a score of 1

The characteristics of the respondents that will be outlined below reflect how the respondents' state of study includes gender, age, and last education.

Validity Testing

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Item 1	17,1000	22,207	,688	,601	,893
Item 2	17,1000	21,193	,854	,872	,868
Item 3	16,9429	23,301	,632	,707	,901
Item 4	17,0286	22,782	,670	,558	,895
Item 5	17,0714	21,198	,849	,869	,868
Item 6	16,9000	22,845	,725	,769	,887

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

From the table above the output SPSS known the value of the validity in the Corrected Item-Total Correlation column means the correlation value between the score of each item and the total score on the respondent's response tabulation. The result of the validity of the 6 (six) statement item in the leader orientation variable is valid (valid) as all values of the coefficient are greater than 0.30.

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Item 1	17,4000	20,910	,837	,790	,882
Item 2	17,4857	22,688	,650	,544	,910
Item 3	17,2429	24,158	,577	,449	,918
Item 4	17,3857	21,516	,791	,766	,889
Item 5	17,2857	21,540	,824	,741	,884
Item 6	17,3429	21,330	,835	,744	,883

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

From the table above the output SPSS known the value of the validity in the Corrected Item-Total Correlation column means the correlation value between the score of each item and the total score on the respondent's response tabulation. The result of the validity of the 6 (six) statement item in the leader orientation variable is valid (valid) as all values of the coefficient are greater than 0.30.

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Item 1	17,3143	18,219	,890	,870	,861
Item 2	17,2571	20,107	,723	,569	,887
Item 3	17,3571	20,146	,580	,348	,912
Item 4	17,2429	18,679	,800	,696	,875
Item 5	17,0429	20,969	,734	,621	,887
Item 6	17,2143	20,142	,717	,740	,888

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

From table above SPSS output result known validity value is found in Corrected Item-Total Correlation column which means correlation value between each item score with total score on Respondent response tabulation. The result of the validity of the 6 (six) statement item in the leader orientation variable is valid (valid) as all values of the coefficient are greater than 0.30.

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Item 1	17,3000	18,097	,622	.	,800
Item 2	17,5571	18,221	,569	.	,811
Item 3	17,3143	18,682	,623	.	,800
Item 4	17,5571	18,221	,569	.	,811
Item 5	17,2714	19,708	,490	.	,825
Item 6	17,4286	16,886	,748	.	,772

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

From table above SPSS output result known validity value is found in Corrected Item-Total Correlation column which means correlation value between each item score with total score on Respondent response tabulation. The result of the validity of the 6 (six) statement item in the leader orientation variable is valid (valid) as all values of the coefficient are greater than 0.30.

Reliability Testing

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
,903	,903	6

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

From the table above, the output of SPSS is known to Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.903 > 0.060 so that it can be concluded that the statement that has been presented to respondents consisting of 6 items of statements in the variables orientation of the leader is reliable or said reliably.

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
,911	,910	6

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

From the table above, the output of SPSS is known to Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.911 > 0.060 so that it can be concluded that the statement that has been presented to the respondent consisting of 6 items of

statement on the variables of the spirit of work is reliable or said reliably.

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
,903	,906	6

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

From the table above, SPSS output is known to Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.903 > 0.060 so that it can be concluded that the statement that has been presented to the respondent consisting of 6 items statements on the environment variables are reliable or said to be reliable.

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
,831	,831	6

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

From the table above, the output of SPSS is known to Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.831 > 0.060 so that it can be concluded that the statement that has been presented to the respondent consisting of 6 items of statement on the performance variable is reliable or it is said reliably.

Testing The Classic Assumption Test Data Normality

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23
Figure 1 Histogram Test Normality

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23
Figure 2 PP Plot Test Normality

Multicollinearity Test

Table 9 Multicollinearity Test Coefficients ^a		
Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	
	Leader Orientation	,417
	Spirit	,143
	Environmenta	,114

a. Dependent Variable: Performance
Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

Based on the table seen above that the VIP Figure Dreamer Orientation is $2.399 < 10$, the Working spirit is $6.973 < 10$, the Working Environment $8.746 < 10$, and the tolerance orientation of the leader $0.417 > 0.10$, the spirit of work $0.143 > 0.10$, and the working environment $0.114 > 0.10$.

Heteroskedasticity Test

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23
Figure 3 Scatterplot heteroskedasticity Test

Table 10 Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Performance	20,8857	5,04916	70
Leader Orientation	20,4286	5,60686	70
Spirit	20,8286	5,58199	70
Environment	20,6857	5,27654	70

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

According to table, it appears that the average value of the performance variable is 20.8857 with the default deviation being 5.04916. For the leader orientation variable the average value is 20.4286 with the default deviation is 5.60686. For a working spirit variable the average value is 20.8286 with a standard deviation of 5.58199. As for the working environment variable the average value is 20.6857 with a standard deviation of 5.27654. And the number of respondents (N) amounted to 70.

Hypothesis Testing

Simultaneous significant tests (test F)

Table 11 Simultaneous Tests (Test F) ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1358,871	3	452,957	74,698	,000 ^b
	Residual	400,215	66	6,064		
	Total	1759,086	69			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance
b. Predictors: (Constant), Environment, Leader Orientation, Spirit

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

According to table above, can be seen that $f_{\text{calculate}}$ amounted to 74.698 whereas F_{tabel} of 2.51 can be seen at $\alpha = 0.05$ (see Appendix F table). The significant probability is much smaller than the 0.05 of $0.000 < 0.05$, so regression models can be said that in this research the orientation of leaders, the working spirit, and the work environment in unison have a positive and significant effect on performance. Then the previous hypothesis was accept H1 (reject H0) or the hypothesis received.

Partial Significant Test (Test T)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2,861	1,240				
	Leader orientation	,308	,082	,342	3,762	,000	,417
	Spirit	,120	,140	,133	,857	,395	,143
	Environment	,446	,166	,466	2,685	,009	,114

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

Coefficient of Determination

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,879 ^a	,772	,762	2,46249

a. Predictors: (Constant), Environment, Leader Orientation, Spirit

b. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: Data Processed SPSS Version 23

Based on the table 4.38 above can be seen that the adjusted number of R Square 0.762 which can be called coefficient of determination which in this case means 76.2% performance can be gained and explained by the orientation of leader, work spirit, and work environment. While the remaining $100\% - 76.2\% = 23.8\%$ is explained by other factors.

CONCLUSION

Simultaneous analysis results showed that $f_{\text{calculate}}$ amounted to 74.698 whereas F_{tabel} of 2.51 and significant probability is much smaller than 0.05 ie $0.000 < 0.05$, then there is a positive and significant influence together (simultaneous) leader orientation, working spirit, and work environment to the performance of employees of Hospital Pertamina Pangkalan Brandan.

Results of partial analysis show that $T_{\text{hitung}} 3.762 > 1.667$ and significant $0.000 < 0.05$, then there is a positive and significant influence individually (partial)

leader orientation towards the employee performance of Hospital Pertamina Pangkalan Brandan, $T_{\text{calculate}} 0.857 > T_{\text{tabel}} 1.667$ and significant $0.395 < 0.05$, then no positive and significant influence individually (partial) working spirit towards employee performance of Hospital Pertamina Pangkalan Brandan and $T_{\text{calculate}} 2.685 < T_{\text{tabel}} 0.395$ and significant $0.09 > 0.05$, hence no positive and significant influence individually (partial) work environment against the performance of Hospital Pertamina Pangkalan Brandan.

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